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Text S1: Cohort-specific study characteristics, ethical approval, funding, and acknowledgments.

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Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Central Committee on Research involving Human Subjects in the Netherlands, the Medical Ethical Committees of the participating hospitals, and from the Registration Committee of the Municipality of Amsterdam. Written informed consent was obtained from all participating parents or legal representatives of the children.

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AE works in a unit that is supported by the University of Bristol and UK Medical Research Council (MC_UU_00011/6). The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreements 874739 (LongITools) and 101021566 (ART-HEALTH) pays the salary of AE. The funders had no role in the design of the study, the collection, analysis, or interpretation of the data; the writing of the manuscript, or the decision to submit the manuscript for publication. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and not necessarily those of any funder.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the ALSPAC Ethics and Law Committee and the Local Research Ethics Committees. Informed consent for the use of data collected via questionnaires and clinics was obtained from participants following the recommendations of the ALSPAC Ethics and Law Committee at the time. <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/researchers/research-ethics/>

We are extremely grateful to all of the families who took part in ALSPAC, the midwives for their help in recruiting them, and the whole ALSPAC team, which includes interviewers, computer and laboratory technicians, clerical workers, research scientists, volunteers, managers, receptionists and nurses.

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Ethics approval has been obtained for the main platform study and all of the individual substudies from the Bradford Research Ethics Committee. All participants gave written informed consent.

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The DNBC complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Danish National Committee on Biomedical Research Ethics. Informed consent was obtained from participants upon enrolment.

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The study received approval from the ethics committee (CCPPRB) of Kremlin Bicêtre on 12 December 2002 and from CNIL (Commission Nationale Informatique et Liberté), the French data privacy institution. Women gave written informed consent for themselves and their child. Fathers gave written informed consent for themselves.

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The study sponsors had no role in the study design, data analysis, interpretation of data, or writing of this report.

The general design, all research aims and the specific measurements in the Generation R Study have been approved by the Medical Ethical Committee of the Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam. New measurements will only be embedded in the study after approval of the Medical Ethical Committee. Participants are asked for their written informed consent for the four consecutive phases of the study (prenatally, birth to 4 years, 4–12 years, and from 12 years onwards). At the start of each phase, mothers and their partners receive written and oral information about the study. Even with consent of the parents, when the child is not willing to participate actively, no measurements are performed. From the age of 12 years, children are asked for written informed consent.

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INMA

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The INMA project was approved by the ethics committee in each area. All participants provided written informed consent before enrolment to the study.

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KANC

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MoBa

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The establishment and data collection in MoBa was previously based on a license from the Norwegian Data protection agency and approval from The Regional Committee for Medical Research Ethics, and it is now based on regulations related to the Norwegian Health Registry Act. MoBa is conducted according to the guidelines laid down in the declaration of Helsinki, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. A detailed protocol of the study including the consent can be found elsewhere (<http://www.fhi.no/morogbarn>).

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NINFEA

The NINFEA cohort was initially funded by the Compagnia SanPaolo Foundation and the Piedmont Region. It received funding from European projects: CHICOS (FP7 grant number HEALTH-FP7-2009-241604, LifeCycle (H2020 grant number 733206), ATHLETE (H2020 grant number 874583).

The Ethical Committee of the San Giovanni Battista Hospital and CTO/CRF/Maria Adelaide Hospital of Turin approved the NINFEA study (approval N. 0048362, and subsequent amendments). Informed consent was obtained from all the participants. The authors are grateful to all the participants of the NINFEA cohort.

Table S1. Information on maps, and models selected to calculate residential proximity to green spaces, and NO₂ and PM_{2.5} pollutants for ALSPAC, GenR, EDEN and INMA. Land use regression (LUR) modeling approach developed in the European Study of Cohorts for Air Pollution Effects (ESCAPE) framework. For those cohorts for which ESCAPE local models were not available, models developed within the ELAPSE project have been used.

Cohort	Maps of urban green spaces		NO ₂	PM _{2.5}
	Source	Year	Source	Source
ABCD	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-
ALSPAC	Urban Atlas	2006	ELAPSE	ELAPSE
BiB	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-
DNBC	Urban Atlas	2006		
EDEN-Nancy	Urban Atlas	2006	ESCAPE local LUR Nancy	ELAPSE
EDEN-Poitiers	Urban Atlas	2006	ESCAPE local LUR Poitiers	ELAPSE
GenR	Urban Atlas	2006	LUR Netherlands and Belgium	LUR Netherlands and Belgium
INMA-Gipuzkoa	EUNIS	2009	LUR Basque Country, Spain	ELAPSE
INMA-Sabadell	Urban Atlas	2006	LUR Catalunya, Spain	LUR Catalunya, Spain
INMA-Valencia	Urban Atlas	2006	LUR Mid-East Spain, Spain	ELAPSE
KANC	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-
MoBA	Kartverket (The Norwegian Mapping Authority)	2014	-	-
NINFEA-Turin	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-

NINFEA-Roma	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-
NINFEA-Florence	Urban Atlas	2006	-	-

Table S1.1 Landsat image details for calculating residential surrounding green spaces and distribution of geocodes, exposures, and outcomes by cohort and child's age year.

Cohort	sub-sample year of birth (1)	Information on geocodes assigned to create a year-by-year estimates of residential surrounding green spaces												Landsat image				
		Pregnancy	y1	y2	y3	y4	y5	y6	y7	y8	y9	y10	y11	y12	Source	Years		
ABCD	2004 (1)	x					x						x		Landsat 4-5-8 Thematic Mapper	2005 & 2006	2010	2015 & 2016
ALSPAC	1992 (1)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Landsat 4-5-7 Thematic Mapper	1990	1994	2002
BIB	2009 (2)	x													Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2006	-	-
DNBC	2000 (2)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	1994	2001	2006
EDEN	2004 (1)	x					x								Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2001, 2004, 2005	2007, 2010 & 2011	-
GENR	2004 (2)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2005 & 2006	2010	2015 & 2016
INMA	2005 (2)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Landsat 4-5-7-8 Thematic Mapper	2001, 2003, 2007	2009, 2010, 2011	2015 & 2017
KANC	2008 (1)	x													Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2007	-	-
MOBA	2007 (2)	x			x		x		x						Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2009	-	-
NINFEA	2010 (5)	x				x			x				x		Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper	2005 & 2007	2007, 2010, 2011 & 2013	2013, 2017 & 2018
Ever asthma:							MOBA	BIB & EDEN		ALSPAC & INMA	GENR & NINFEA		DNBC					
Current Wheezing episodes:								EDEN		INMA & NINFEA	GENR		ALSPAC & DNBC					
Lung function:								EDEN	INMA	ALSPAC	GENR							
BMI:							KANC		BIB, MOBA & NINFEA	ABCD, EDEN, GENR	INMA		DNBC	ALSPAC				
Blood pressure:								EDEN	INMA	BIB & GENR				ALSPAC				
Non-verbal intelligence:								EDEN	GENR	ALSPAC & INMA				ABCD				
Internalizing problems:									BIB	EDEN	GENR	ABCD	ALSPAC & DNBC					
Externalizing problems:									BIB	EDEN	GENR & ABCD	ABCD	ALSPAC, DNBC & INMA					
ADHD symptoms:										EDEN	GENR & ABCD	ABCD	ALSPAC, DNBC & INMA					
Outcomes in childhood							Distribution of outcomes per cohort in the study subsample based on assesment year (mean age)											

(I) Median (IQR)

y_k = year of the child

x = timepoints with exact residential address geocoded

x = year of exposure measurement selected in each cohort

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↓ read from top to bottom

Table S2. Details of data collected on covariates at recruitment, during pregnancy or at birth in participating cohorts

Covariate	ABCD	ALSPAC	BIB	DNBC	EDEN	Gen R	INMA	KANC	MoBa	NINFE A
Sex of the child	Birth records	Birth records	Birth records	National identity register	Paediatric report	Clinical records	Clinical records	Questionnaire	Questionnaire, Medical Birth Registry	Questionnaire
Mother height and weight (pre-pregnancy)	Self-reported	Self-reported	Measured	Self-reported	Self-reported	Measured	Measured	Self-report	Questionnaire	Self-reported
Maternal age at birth (years)	Self-reported	Calculated from maternal date of birth and reported delivery date	Administrative cohort information	Medical birth registry	Obstetrical report and inclusion report	Questionnaire (calculated from date of birth reported in questionnaire at enrolment, and date of delivery)	Medical birth registry	Medical birth registry	Medical birth registry	Questionnaire (pregnancy and 6 months)
Maternal smoking in pregnancy (yes/no)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Interview by midwife	Questionnaire (enrolment)	Questionnaire (pregnancy 12th and 32th week)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)
Parity Multipara/ Nullipara	Mothers' parity based on previous born children	The number of previous pregnancies resulting in either a livebirth or a stillbirth.	Registerable parity	Information about previous live and still births	Previous born children (previous stillbirths included, abortions excluded)	Previous born children (previous stillbirths included, abortions excluded)	Mothers' parity based on previous born children (previous stillbirths included, abortions excluded)	Information about previous live and still births	Previous born children (previous stillbirths included, abortions excluded)	Mothers' parity based on previous born children

Table S2. (continue) Details of data collected on covariates at recruitment, during pregnancy or at birth in participating cohorts

Covariate	ABCD	ALSPAC	BIB	DNBC	EDEN	Gen R	INMA	KANC	MoBa	NINFEA
Maternal education: highest on-going or completed education when child was between >-1 and <1 year*	Questionnaire (child one year of birth)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Phone interview (pregnancy)	Interview by midwife	Questionnaire (enrolment)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)
Maternal ethnic background	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	NA	Interview by midwife	Questionnaire (enrolment)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	Questionnaire (pregnancy)	NA	Questionnaire

NA – Not available;

Table S3. Details of data collected on respiratory outcomes in participating cohorts

Cohort	Ever Asthma	Current Wheezing	Lung function
ABCD	-	-	-
ALSPAC	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Maternal report of child taking asthma medication in past 12 months Maternal report of child wheezing or whistling in the past 12 months Maternal report of child diagnosis of asthma or eczema by doctor Partially harmonized as MEDAL or ISAAC questionnaires not used.	Maternal report of child wheeze in the past 12 months Partially harmonized as based on maternal report rather than use of ISAAC questionnaire	FEV ₁ , FVC and FEV ₁ /FVC were measured by spirometry according to the ATS/ERS guidelines and converted to Z-scores for age, height, sex and ethnicity based on the Global Lung Initiative 2012 reference values.
BiB	Asthma read codes were used to select for children who have a doctor diagnosis of asthma using Read codes (Partially harmonized)	-	NA
DNBC	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Has [child name] ever had asthma?	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Has your child had wheezing or whistling in the chest in the last 12 months?	NA
EDEN	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Diagnosis of asthma within since birth	Ascertained by parental questionnaire: Wheezing of the child	FEV ₁ , FVC and FEV ₁ /FVC were measured by spirometry according to the ATS/ERS guidelines and converted to Z-scores for age, height, sex and ethnicity based on the Global Lung Initiative 2012 reference values.

Table S3 (continued). Details of data collected on respiratory outcomes in participating cohorts

Cohort	Ever Asthma	Current Wheezing	Lung function
GenR	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Ever physician diagnosed asthma?	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Wheezing in the chest in the last 12 months	FEV ₁ , FVC and FEV ₁ /FVC were measured by spirometry according to the ATS/ERS guidelines and converted to Z-scores for age, height, sex and ethnicity based on the Global Lung Initiative 2012 reference values.
INMA	Self-administered parental questionnaire: Has your child been diagnosed by a doctor as having asthma?	Ascertained by self-administered parental questionnaire: Has your child had wheezing or whistling in the chest in the past 12 months?	FEV ₁ , FVC and FEV ₁ /FVC were measured by spirometry according to the ATS/ERS guidelines and converted to Z-scores for age, height, sex and ethnicity based on the Global Lung Initiative 2012 reference values.
KANC	NA	NA	NA
MoBA	Ascertained by parental questionnaire (partially harmonized): Has the child now or have it ever had any of the following diseases or health problems? If yes, does the child still have the illness /problem? Item: asthma	NA	NA
NINFEA	Ascertained by parental questionnaire: Q6 (7 years of age): The combination of the two questions: "Has your child ever had asthma?" and "Has a doctor ever told you that you child had asthma?"	Ascertained by parental questionnaire: Has your child had wheezing or whistling in the chest in the past 12 months?	NA

NA – Not available;

Table S4. Details of data collected on cardiometabolic outcomes in participating cohorts

Cohort	Child BMI (method of height and weight measurement)	Blood pressure
ABCD	Clinical measurement and medical record	NA
ALSPAC	Clinical measurement	Blood pressure measured twice with the participant sitting and at rest with their arm supported, using a cuff size appropriate for their upper arm circumference and an Omron IntelliSense M6 (Omron Healthcare, Kyoto, Japan).
BiB	Clinical measurement	NA
DNBC	Self-report	NA
EDEN	Clinical measurement and self-report	Blood pressure measured left arm three times at 2-minute intervals at research clinics Oscillometric COLIN 8800 C
GenR	Clinical measurement	At age 6 and 10, SBP and DBP were measured four times with 1-minute intervals at the right brachial artery, while the child was lying quietly in a supine position. We used the validated automatic sphygmomanometer Datascope Accutorr Plus™ (Paramus, NJ, USA). A cuff was selected with a cuff width approximately 40% of the arm circumference and long enough to cover 90% of the arm circumference.
INMA	Clinical measurement and self-report	Blood pressure was taken in sitting position three consecutive times with 1 min intervals. OMRON 705-CPII automated oscillometric device.
KANC	Clinical measurement and self-report	NA
MoBa	Self-report	NA
NINFEA	Self-reported	NA

NA - not available

Table S5. Details of data collected on neurodevelopmental outcomes in participating cohorts

Cohort	Non-verbal intelligence	Internalization problems	Externalization problems	ADHD
ABCD (Netherlands)	RPM - Raven's Progressive Matrices Evaluator: examiner	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: teacher and parent (33.57)	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: teacher and parent (33.57)	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: teacher and parent (33.57)
ALSPAC (UK)	WISC - Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (n=227) WPPSI- Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence (96.8%) Evaluator: examiner	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent
BiB (UK)	NA	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	NA
DNBC (Denmark)	NA	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent

Table S5 (continue). Details of data collected on neurodevelopmental outcomes in participating cohorts

Cohort	Non-verbal intelligence	Internalization problems	Externalization problems	ADHD
EDEN (France)	WPPSI - Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence Evaluator: examiner	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent	SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: parent
GenR (Netherlands)	SON-R Snijders-Oomen Non-Verbal Intelligence Test Evaluator: examiner	CBCL - Child Behaviour Checklist Evaluator: parent	CBCL - Child Behaviour Checklist Evaluator: parent	CPRS-R Revised Conners' Parent Rating Scale Evaluator: Parent
INMA (Spain)	MSCA - McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities RPM - Raven's Progressive Matrices (80%) Evaluator: examiner (n=293) or Computerized (n=1.185)	CBCL - Child Behaviour Checklist SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (47%) Evaluator: parent	CBCL - Child Behaviour Checklist SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (47%) Evaluator: Parent	CPRS-R Revised Conners' Parent Rating Scale (93.9%) DISC-IV/DSM Diagnostic Interview Schedule for Children Evaluator: parent and teacher (n=4%)
MoBa (Norway)	NA	NA	NA	-
NINFEA (Italy)	NA	NA	NA	DISC-IV/DSM Diagnostic Interview Schedule for Children & SDQ - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire Evaluator: Parent

NA – Not available;

Table S6. Distribution of traffic-related air pollutants levels within cohorts with lung function measures.

Variables	ALSPAC (n=13491)	EDEN (n=1999)	GenR (n=9283)	INMA (n=2084)
NO² concentration (µg/m³) pregnancy	27 (4.2)	21.8 (10.2)	37.9 (5.5)	28.2 (15.8)
Missing	1560	109	76	70
NO² concentration (µg/m³) childhood²	22 (3.6)	18.8 (8.3)	29.7 (6.2)	25.4 (13.4)
Missing	1560	109	243	80
PM_{2.5} concentration (µg/m³) pregnancy	13.3 (0.7)	16.7 (1.4)	19.0 (1.9)	14.9 (2.5)
Missing	1560	109	76	85
PM_{2.5} concentration1 (µg/m³) childhood²	11.1 (0.7)	15.6 (1.5)	15.9 (1.6)	14.0 (1.7)
Missing	1560	341	243	114

²measures at 8 years of age for ALSPAC; 5 years of age for EDEN; 8 years of age for GenR; 6 years of age for INMA

Figure S1 to S12: Cohort-specific estimates for exposures to green spaces and child health outcomes. Cohort's outcome-specific regression models. The dot in the forest plot represents the adjusted estimates, while the whiskers span the 95% CI. Estimates represented by Beta coefficient or OR and corresponding 95% CI. Regression estimates are represented per 1-IQR increase in each exposure. Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI; Models from EDEN, INMA, NINFEA were further adjusted for sub-cohort. Models from ABCD, BiB and GenR were further adjusted for maternal ethnic background; Weight, cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects meta-analysis (inversed-variance). CI, confidence interval; OR, Odds ratio.

Figure S1. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and ever asthma (yes)

Figure S2. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and current wheezing (yes)

Figure S3. Forest plot of associations between and exposures to green spaces and Lung function (Forced expiratory volume in the 1 second - FEV₁ z-score)

Figure S4. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and Lung function (Forced vital capacity z-score).

Figure S5. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and Lung function (FEV₁/FVC ratio z-score).

Figure S6. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and BMI z-score.

Figure S7: Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and Systolic blood pressure (mmHg).

Figure S8. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg).

Figure S9. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and Non-verbal intelligence (standardize scores)

Figure S10. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and internalizing problems (z-score)

NDVI pregnancy

NDVI childhood

Linear distance (m) pregnancy

Linear distance (m) childhood

Figure S11. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and externalizing problems (z-score)

Figure S12. Forest plot of associations between exposures to green spaces and ADHD

Table S7 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and respiratory outcomes stratified by maternal education (high level vs. medium/low level reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Medium-low maternal education						High maternal education				
Ever asthma (Yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	13005	1.13	(0.98,1.30)	0.094	41.32	15662	0.96	(0.87,1.07)	0.473	13.84
NDVI_childhood	9388	1.06	(0.94,1.18)	0.336	12.89	12159	1.00	(0.91,1.10)	0.964	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	12715	1.03	(0.94,1.12)	0.582	16.72	15418	0.98	(0.88,1.09)	0.692	29.70
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	9004	0.98	(0.91,1.06)	0.616	0.03	11852	0.96	(0.88,1.05)	0.401	0.04
Current wheezing (yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	10699	1.00	(0.87,1.13)	0.954	19.03	9032	1.00	(0.83,1.20)	0.990	48.89
NDVI_childhood	9785	1.07	(0.98,1.16)	0.153	0.01	6540	0.90	(0.74,1.10)	0.301	51.57
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10385	0.99	(0.89,1.10)	0.906	18.23	8785	0.95	(0.85,1.06)	0.335	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	9366	0.95	(0.85,1.06)	0.398	17.20	6226	1.00	(0.88,1.12)	0.939	0.00
Lung function (FEV₁-zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4763	0.02	(-0.02,0.06)	0.388	0.72	3231	0.02	(-0.04,0.09)	0.458	32.62
NDVI_childhood	4728	0.08	(0.04,0.12)	<0.001	0.00	3180	0.03	(-0.02,0.07)	0.224	0.00

Linear distance (m)_pregnancy	4605	-0.00	(-0.07,0.06)	0.912	66.95
Linear distance (m)_childhood	4522	-0.03	(-0.09,0.03)	0.368	61.48
Lung function (FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4738	0.01	(-0.03,0.05)	0.537	0.00
NDVI_childhood	4703	0.08	(0.04,0.12)	<0.001	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	4580	-0.00	(-0.04,0.03)	0.947	0.12
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	4497	-0.02	(-0.05,0.02)	0.269	3.21
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4738	-0.00	(-0.04,0.04)	0.999	0.17
NDVI_childhood	4703	0.01	(-0.07,0.08)	0.693	59.23
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	4580	-0.01	(-0.04,0.03)	0.892	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	4497	0.00	(-0.06,0.07)	0.877	64.95

3074	-0.03	(-0.08,0.02)	0.296	28.60
2966	-0.07	(-0.12, -0.03)	<0.001	0.00
n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
3220	0.01	(-0.04,0.06)	0.688	0.18
3169	0.04	(0,0.08)	0.070	0.00
3063	-0.03	(-0.1,0.03)	0.338	53.67
2955	-0.08	(-0.12, -0.04)	<0.001	0.00
n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
3220	0.00	(-0.05,0.05)	0.984	0.00
3169	-0.02	(-0.07,0.02)	0.299	0.00
3063	0.01	(-0.05,0.06)	0.826	27.38
2955	0.02	(-0.03,0.07)	0.394	16.71

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pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, area-level SES, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI and specific-cohort adjustment. **Bold = p values corrected for multiple testing.**

Table S8 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and cardiometabolic outcomes stratified by maternal education (high level vs. medium/low level reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Medium-low maternal education						High maternal education				
BMI (z-score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	16538	0.01	(-0.02,0.04)	0.382	2.47	18677	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.855	0.00
NDVI_childhood	12781	0.00	(-0.03,0.03)	0.382	0.13	14559	-0.01	(-0.03,0.02)	0.600	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	16231	-0.02	(-0.05,0.01)	0.863	12.21	18425	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.305	0.24
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	12339	-0.01	(-0.04,0.01)	0.417	0.00	14107	-0.00	(-0.02,0.02)	0.847	0.22
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	10552	0.16	(-0.1,0.42)	0.239	0.00	5064	0.07	(-0.52,0.66)	0.824	57.26
NDVI_childhood	8458	0.24	(-0.1,0.58)	0.619	21.69	4206	-0.02	(-0.33,0.28)	0.876	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10268	-0.06	(-0.29,0.17)	0.163	0.00	4824	-0.04	(-0.37,0.29)	0.806	17.56
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	8081	-0.13	(-0.36,0.11)	0.286	0.00	3902	-0.22	(-0.5,0.07)	0.133	0.00
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	10552	0.05	(-0.33,0.43)	0.793	48.16	5065	-0.22	(-0.59,0.16)	0.254	29.69
NDVI_childhood	8458	0.16	(-0.28,0.59)	0.727	61.13	4207	-0.53	(-0.91, -0.16)	0.005	37.29

Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10268	-0.03	(-0.22,0.16)	0.489	0.00	4825	0.07	(-0.16,0.31)	0.541	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	8081	-0.02	(-0.21,0.17)	0.850	0.00	3902	-0.07	(-0.42,0.28)	0.694	47.59

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, area-level SES smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment.

Table S9 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and neurodevelopmental outcomes stratified by maternal education (high level vs. medium/low level reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Medium-low maternal education						High maternal education				
Non-verbal intelligence (standardize score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	7674	-0.54	(-1.49,0.40)	0.259	58.48	4831	-0.35	(-1.52,0.83)	0.562	71.10
NDVI_childhood	7606	0.32	(-0.12,0.76)	0.158	0.00	4746	-0.07	(-0.66,0.51)	0.801	13.20
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	7433	0.25	(-0.16,0.67)	0.233	0.00	4625	0.17	(-0.32,0.66)	0.495	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	7257	0.05	(-0.35,0.45)	0.805	0.00	4385	0.09	(-0.39,0.58)	0.715	0.00
Int. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	12452	-0.01	(-0.05,0.03)	0.648	48.2	15422	0.01	(-0.01,0.04)	0.274	0.00
NDVI_childhood	10839	-0.01	(-0.05,0.04)	0.772	47.6	12694	0.01	(-0.03,0.04)	0.672	43.14
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	12159	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.734	25.3	15179	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.947	30.17
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	10387	-0.00	(-0.03,0.03)	0.828	31.2	12200	-0.01	(-0.04,0.02)	0.660	51.12
Ext. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	12235	-0.01	(-0.04,0.03)	0.757	24.22	15808	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.690	0.36
NDVI_childhood	10625	-0.01	(-0.05,0.03)	0.639	42.24	13094	0.01	(-0.02,0.04)	0.441	34.36
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	11938	-0.01	(-0.03,0.02)	0.631	11.49	15567	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.390	10.58
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	10180	-0.01	(-0.04,0.03)	0.670	39.31					
ADHD (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²

NDVI_pregnancy	10555	-0.00	(-0.03,0.03)	0.901	21.3	14390	0.01	(-0.01,0.02)	0.424	14390
NDVI_childhood	9561	-0.02	(-0.04,0.00)	0.074	0	11666	0.01	(-0.02,0.03)	0.600	11666
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10254	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.263	0	14145	-0.02	(-0.04,0)	0.074	14145
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	9164	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.760	32.2	11356	-0.04	(-0.08, -0.01)	0.023	11356

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, area-level SES smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment.

Table S10 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and respiratory outcomes stratified by SES area-level deprivation (high level vs. medium/low deprived reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

High socio economic deprivation index						Medium-low socio economic deprivation index				
Ever asthma (Yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	11687	1.02	(0.94,1.12)	0.597	0.01	16729	1.04	(0.94,1.14)	0.447	18.32
NDVI_childhood	7865	1.03	(0.94,1.13)	0.517	0.00	13471	1.04	(0.92,1.17)	0.542	33.37
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	11555	1.06	(0.98,1.15)	0.171	0.00	16327	0.98	(0.91,1.05)	0.555	0.01
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	7661	1.02	(0.93,1.12)	0.658	0.00	12984	0.94	(0.87,1.01)	0.082	0.01
Current wheezing (yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	6544	1.02	(0.91,1.14)	0.752	0.01	12934	-0.00	(-0.11,0.11)	0.997	18.65
NDVI_childhood	5795	1.09	(0.97,1.22)	0.156	0.01	10319	-0.09	(-0.29,0.11)	0.367	60.03
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	6408	0.97	(0.87,1.09)	0.649	0.00	12509	-0.04	(-0.12,0.05)	0.407	0.01
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	5582	0.92	(0.77,1.10)	0.366	30.97	9799	-0.01	(-0.1,0.08)	0.830	0.01
Lung function (FEV₁-zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	3188	-0.01	(-0.06,0.05)	0.823	0.00	4806	0.03	(-0.03,0.08)	0.365	44.32
NDVI_childhood	3154	0.06	(0.01,0.11)	0.011	0.00	4754	0.05	(0,0.1)	0.044	29.42

Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3099	0.03	(-0.01,0.08)	0.095	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3020	-0.02	(-0.06,0.02)	0.359	0.09
Lung function (FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	3182	-0.01	(-0.08,0.07)	0.821	31.60
NDVI_childhood	3148	0.06	(0.01,0.1)	0.011	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3093	0.04	(0,0.08)	0.083	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3014	-0.02	(-0.06,0.02)	0.246	0.00
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	3182	-0.01	(-0.06,0.05)	0.848	0.00
NDVI_childhood	3148	-0.01	(-0.06,0.04)	0.713	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3093	-0.00	(-0.05,0.04)	0.853	0.04
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3014	0.01	(-0.03,0.05)	0.749	0.00

4580	-0.05	(-0.08, -0.01)	0.011	0.00
4468	-0.05	(-0.09, -0.02)	0.002	0.00
n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
4776	0.02	(-0.03,0.07)	0.452	27.27
4724	0.07	(0.03,0.1)	<0.001	0.00
4550	-0.04	(-0.07,0)	0.041	0.70
4438	-0.05	(-0.09, -0.02)	0.004	16.27
n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
4776	0.00	(-0.04,0.04)	0.903	0.00
4724	-0.02	(-0.08,0.05)	0.638	60.21
4550	-0.00	(-0.06,0.05)	0.910	48.89
4438	0.01	(-0.05,0.08)	0.700	73.02

pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment. **Bold = p values corrected for multiple testing.**

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Table S11 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and cardiometabolic outcomes stratified by SES area-level deprivation (high level vs. medium/low deprived reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

High socio economic deprivation index						Medium-low socio economic deprivation index				
BMI (z-score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	15780	0.00	(-0.03,0.04)	0.774	16.34	19077	0.01	(-0.01,0.03)	0.419	0.00
NDVI_childhood	11729	0.00	(-0.03,0.03)	0.948	0.00	15332	0.00	(-0.02,0.02)	0.971	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	15638	-0.02	(-0.04,0)	0.053	0.09	18660	-0.01	(-0.04,0.01)	0.324	25.88
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	11424	-0.01	(-0.04,0.01)	0.345	6.52	14743	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.780	23.34
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	7579	-0.05	(-0.37,0.27)	0.747	0.00	8037	0.32	(0.01,0.64)	0.044	15.37
NDVI_childhood	5167	-0.21	(-0.75,0.33)	0.451	51.43	7497	0.26	(-0.01,0.52)	0.055	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	7451	0.03	(-0.22,0.28)	0.811	0.00	7641	-0.18	(-0.43,0.08)	0.177	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	4971	0.05	(-0.37,0.46)	0.828	35.03	7012	-0.23	(-0.47,0.01)	0.065	0.00
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	7579	0.01	(-0.32,0.35)	0.576	25.46	8038	-0.08	(-0.3,0.13)	0.450	0.00
NDVI_childhood	5167	-0.15	(-0.46,0.16)	0.351	19.33	7498	-0.20	(-0.41,0.02)	0.076	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	7451	0.07	(-0.14,0.27)	0.586	0.00	7642	-0.06	(-0.3,0.18)	0.622	12.58
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	4971	-0.04	(-0.26,0.19)	0.749	0.00	7012	-0.05	(-0.25,0.15)	0.638	0.00

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment.

Table S12 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and neurodevelopmental outcomes stratified by SES area-level deprivation (high level vs. medium/low deprived reported). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

High socio economic deprivation index						Medium-low socio economic deprivation index				
Non-verbal intelligence (standardize score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²
NDVI_pregnancy	5305	-0.70	(-1.48,0.07)	0.076	27.90	7407	-0.25	(-1.08,0.58)	0.554	60.54
NDVI_childhood	5225	0.10	(-0.43,0.63)	0.711	1.35	7286	0.25	(-0.18,0.69)	0.252	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	5198	0.17	(-0.30,0.64)	0.478	0.00	7024	0.29	(-0.13,0.71)	0.173	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	4978	0.06	(-0.41,0.53)	0.797	0.00	6788	0.12	(-0.28,0.52)	0.551	0.00
Int. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²
NDVI_pregnancy	11316	-0.01	(-0.06,0.04)	0.704	64.09	16558	-0.00	(-0.04,0.03)	0.874	52.43
NDVI_childhood	9710	0.01	(-0.05,0.07)	0.702	71.30	13823	-0.02	(-0.05,0.01)	0.318	36.99
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	11183	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.751	1.53	16155	0.01	(-0.01,0.03)	0.541	0.17
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	9370	-0.01	(-0.04,0.01)	0.350	10.74	13217	0.01	(-0.01,0.03)	0.213	9.69
Ext. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I ²
NDVI_pregnancy	11150	0.01	(-0.02,0.04)	0.538	5.17	16893	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.803	19.22
NDVI_childhood	9554	0.02	(-0.02,0.06)	0.337	41.44	14165	-0.02	(-0.04,0)	0.100	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	11017	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.840	0.00	16488	-0.01	(-0.03,0)	0.143	0.06
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	9245	-0.02	(-0.05,0)	0.107	9.74	13582	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.391	0.00

ADHD (zscore)						n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	8366	0.01	(-0.01,0.03)	0.347	0.00	16573	0.00	(-0.01,0.02)	0.801	0.16
NDVI_childhood	7502	-0.00	(-0.02,0.02)	0.917	0.00	13720	-0.01	(-0.03,0)	0.045	0.04
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	8233	-0.00	(-0.02,0.02)	0.882	0.00	16160	-0.02	(-0.03,0)	0.040	11.07
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	7301	-0.01	(-0.04,0.02)	0.505	21.54	13214	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.184	25.70

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI and specific-cohort adjustment.

Table S13 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and respiratory outcomes stratified by child sex Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Female						Male				
Ever asthma (Yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	14186	1.09	(0.96,1.25)	0.176	33.95	14635	1.00	(0.93,1.07)	0.945	0.00
NDVI_childhood	10717	1.10	(0.96,1.26)	0.185	29.63	10951	0.99	(0.92,1.07)	0.830	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	13939	1.03	(0.95,1.12)	0.485	0.00	14348	1.00	(0.92,1.08)	0.934	18.29
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	10386	1.00	(0.91,1.09)	0.981	0.00	10591	0.96	(0.89,1.03)	0.256	0.00
Current wheezing (yes/no)	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	OR	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	9762	1.00	(0.90,1.11)	0.988	0.00	10125	0.99	(0.83,1.18)	0.897	58.40
NDVI_childhood	8099	0.96	(0.77,1.19)	0.695	56.15	8349	0.94	(0.78,1.13)	0.513	54.58
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	9499	1.00	(0.90,1.11)	0.995	0.00	9827	0.96	(0.88,1.05)	0.394	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	7742	1.00	(0.90,1.12)	0.933	0.00	7973	0.95	(0.85,1.06)	0.331	16.04
Lung function (FEV₁-zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4049	0.04	(0,0.09)	0.050	0.00	3945	-0.01	(-0.05,0.04)	0.758	0.00
NDVI_childhood	4004	0.06	(0.02,0.1)	0.004	0.00	3904	0.06	(0.01,0.1)	0.008	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3901	-0.03	(-0.08,0.01)	0.175	25.83	3778	0.00	(-0.04,0.04)	0.984	14.31
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3799	-0.04	(-0.08,0)	0.040	0.00	3689	-0.05	(-0.1,0)	0.047	32.97

Lung function (FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4037	0.03	(-0.01,0.07)	0.189	0.00	3921	-0.01	(-0.05,0.04)	0.813	0.00
NDVI_childhood	3992	0.07	(0.03,0.12)	<0.001	0.00	3880	0.05	(0.01,0.1)	0.015	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3889	-0.02	(-0.07,0.02)	0.376	22.40	3754	-0.00	(-0.05,0.04)	0.890	15.31
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3787	-0.05	(-0.08, -0.01)	0.016	0.00	3665	-0.04	(-0.08,0)	0.030	0.13
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC _{-zscore})	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	4037	0.01	(-0.03,0.06)	0.600	0.04	3921	-0.01	(-0.06,0.04)	0.747	0.00
NDVI_childhood	3992	-0.04	(-0.08,0)	0.062	0.00	3880	0.01	(-0.04,0.05)	0.707	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	3889	-0.01	(-0.05,0.02)	0.472	0.00	3754	0.02	(-0.04,0.08)	0.564	48.32
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	3787	0.02	(-0.03,0.07)	0.378	43.97	3665	-0.01	(-0.04,0.03)	0.790	0.00

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age, SES area level deprivation, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment. **Bold = p values corrected for multiple testing.**

Table S14 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and cardiometabolic outcomes stratified by child sex. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Female						Male				
BMI (z-score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	17478	0.00	(-0.02,0.03)	0.869	16.69	17929	0.01	(-0.02,0.04)	0.592	31.80
NDVI_childhood	13629	-0.01	(-0.03,0.02)	0.603	12.00	13862	-0.00	(-0.04,0.03)	0.881	34.92
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	17214	-0.01	(-0.03,0.02)	0.598	4.38	17634	-0.02	(-0.05,0.01)	0.168	42.62
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	13202	-0.00	(-0.02,0.02)	0.901	8.89	13395	-0.00	(-0.04,0.03)	0.796	54.09
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)						n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	7737	0.17	(-0.13,0.46)	0.265	0.00	7879	0.17	(-0.12,0.46)	0.248	0.00
NDVI_childhood	6273	0.11	(-0.18,0.4)	0.454	0.00	6391	0.15	(-0.13,0.43)	0.305	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	7496	0.03	(-0.23,0.29)	0.814	0.00	7596	-0.17	(-0.42,0.08)	0.187	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	5952	0.06	(-0.2,0.32)	0.666	0.00	6031	-0.40	(-0.65, -0.14)	0.002	0.00
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)						n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	7738	0.04	(-0.2,0.28)	0.754	0.00	7879	-0.12	(-0.45,0.22)	0.494	33.03
NDVI_childhood	6274	-0.09	(-0.32,0.15)	0.469	0.00	6391	-0.25	(-0.48, -0.02)	0.035	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	7497	-0.09	(-0.3,0.12)	0.411	0.00	7596	0.02	(-0.28,0.33)	0.877	43.40
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	5952	-0.09	(-0.3,0.13)	0.429	0.00	6031	-0.05	(-0.26,0.16)	0.645	0.01

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age, SES area level deprivation, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment.

Table S15 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and neurodevelopmental outcomes stratified by child sex. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Female						Male				
Non-verbal intelligence (standardize score)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	6209	-0.29	(-1.27,0.68)	0.556	63.87		-0.60	(-1.36,0.15)	0.116	39.11
NDVI_childhood	6133	-0.15	(-1.04,0.73)	0.735	63.11		0.32	(-0.17,0.80)	0.199	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	6001	0.16	(-0.64,0.95)	0.701	67.51		0.28	(-0.25,0.81)	0.303	19.89
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	5806	0.15	(-0.39,0.70)	0.583	34.75		-0.08	(-0.55,0.39)	0.735	7.78
Int. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	11123	-0.02	(-0.06,0.02)	0.388	45.74	11265	0.01	(-0.04,0.06)	0.691	59.22
NDVI_childhood	8988	-0.01	(-0.05,0.04)	0.759	59.84	9060	0.02	(-0.04,0.07)	0.560	68.84
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10866	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.850	0.00	10986	0.01	(-0.02,0.03)	0.530	1.38
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	8535	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.719	0.00	8567	-0.01	(-0.04,0.02)	0.462	7.05
Ext. Problems (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	10835	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.758	0.00	10764	-0.01	(-0.06,0.04)	0.716	61.35
NDVI_childhood	8704	0.00	(-0.03,0.04)	0.851	37.45	8570	-0.01	(-0.06,0.03)	0.656	51.81
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	10582	-0.01	(-0.04,0.01)	0.207	0.00	10479	-0.00	(-0.03,0.02)	0.698	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	8274	-0.02	(-0.05,0.01)	0.157	10.53	8108	-0.01	(-0.03,0.02)	0.526	0.00

ADHD (zscore)	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²	n	β	95%CI	p-value	I²
NDVI_pregnancy	12270	0.00	(-0.01,0.02)	0.693	0.05	12677	0.00	(-0.01,0.02)	0.612	0.03
NDVI_childhood	10480	-0.01	(-0.02,0.01)	0.262	0.00	10748	-0.01	(-0.02,0.01)	0.225	0.10
Linear Distance (m)_pregnancy	12013	-0.01	(-0.03,0.01)	0.248	5.00	12388	-0.01	(-0.03,0)	0.087	0.00
Linear Distance (m)_childhood	10134	-0.02	(-0.04,0.01)	0.186	35.67	10387	-0.00	(-0.02,0.01)	0.663	0.17

n, pooled cohorts' sample; Models are adjusted for: child age, SES area level deprivation, maternal education, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, maternal BMI, and specific-cohort adjustment.

Figure S13. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* for NDVI within 100m and 500m radial buffers around child residential address during pregnancy and childhood and respiratory outcomes. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S14. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* for NDVI within 100m and 500m radial buffers around child residential address during pregnancy and childhood and cardiometabolic outcomes. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S15. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* NDVI within 100m and 500m radial buffers around child residential address during pregnancy and childhood and neurodevelopmental outcomes. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

*Overall adjusted estimates with 95% CIs from IPD meta-analyses of the outcome-specific regression models, where cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects model (inversed-variance). The dot in the forest plot represents the adjusted estimates, while the whiskers span the 95% CI. Estimates represented by Odds ratio (OR) or Beta estimates and corresponding 95% CI. Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI. Sample = pooled cohorts' sample; p = p-value of statistical significance of pooled effect size; I²-statistics (I²); p_{Qtest} = pvalue for heterogeneity Q Cochran's test.

Figure S16 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ever asthma with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S16.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ever asthma with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S16.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ever asthma with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S16.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ever asthma with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure 17 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and current wheezing with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S17.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and current wheezing with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S17.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and current wheezing with .Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S17.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and current wheezing with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S18 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis K times, each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S18.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis K times, each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S18.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis K times, each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S18.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis K times, each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S19 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FVC zscore) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S19.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FVC zscore) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S19.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FVC zscore) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S19.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FVC zscore) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S20- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁/FVC zscore) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S20.1- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁/FVC zscore) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S20.2- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁/FVC zscore) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S20.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Lung Function (FEV₁/FVC zscore) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S21 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and BMI (zscore) with (A) NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S21.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and BMI (zscore) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S21.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and BMI (zscore) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S21.3- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and BMI (zscore) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S22 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Systolic blood pressure (mmHg) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S22.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Systolic blood pressure (mmHg) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S22.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Systolic blood pressure (mmHg) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S22.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Systolic blood pressure (mmHg) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S23- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S23.1- Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S23.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S23.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S24 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Non-verbal intelligence standardize score NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S24.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Non-verbal intelligence standardized score NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S24.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Non-verbal intelligence standardize score Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S24.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Non-verbal intelligence standardize score Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S25 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Internalizing problems (zscore) NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S25.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Internalizing problems (zscore) NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S25.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Internalizing problems (zscore) Linear distance pregnancy.. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S25.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Internalizing problems (zscore) Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S26 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of the main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Externalizing problems (zscore) NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S26.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of the main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Externalizing problems (zscore) NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S26.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of the main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Externalizing problems (zscore) Linear distance pregnancy- Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S26.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of the main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and Externalizing problems (zscore) Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Figure S27 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ADHD symptoms (zscore) with NDVI pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S27.1 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ADHD symptoms (zscore) with NDVI childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S27.2 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ADHD symptoms (zscore) with Linear distance pregnancy. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S27.3 - Leave-one-out recalculate the results of main meta-analysis each time leaving out one study. Pooled effect adjusted estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and ADHD symptoms (zscore) with Linear distance childhood. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure

Figure S28. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* for green spaces exposures and respiratory outcomes in children aged 6-12 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Figure S29. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* for green spaces exposures and cardiometabolic outcomes in children aged 6-12 years.

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Figure S30. Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis* for green spaces exposures and neurodevelopmental outcomes in children aged 6-12 years.

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

Stratified analysis - age greater than or equal to 6 years

*Estimates are represented per 1-IQR increase in each exposure. Overall adjusted estimates with 95% CIs from IPD meta-analyses of the outcome-specific regression models, where cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects model (inversed-variance). The dot in the forest plot represents the adjusted estimates, while the whiskers span the 95% CI. Estimates represented by Odds ratio (OR) or Beta estimates and corresponding 95% CI. Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES, smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI. Sample = pooled cohorts' sample; p = p-value of statistical significance of pooled effect size; I²-statistics (I²); p_Qtest = pvalue for heterogeneity Q Cochran's test.

Table S16 - Results of individual variable meta-regression models for specific outcomes pooled estimates with $I^2 \geq 60\%$, or Cochran's Q test p-value of ≤ 0.05 , or when the 95% confidence interval for τ^2 did not include zero

Exposure vs. Outcome	Estimate	se	95%CI	p-value	Variance accounted for	Test for moderators			Test for residual heterogeneity		
						Q_M	DF	p-value	Q_E	DF	p-value
NDVI childhood vs. Wheezing episodes (yes/no)											
Mean age of outcome assessment	0.99	1.06	(0.86, 1.11)	0.781	0.0	0.07	1	0.781	15.90	4	0.003
NDVI pregnancy vs. Non-verbal intelligence (standardize scores)											
Mean age of assessment	0.27	0.15	(-0.03, 0.57)	0.076	55.1	3.13	1	0.076	5.15	3	0.161
NDVI childhood vs. Non-verbal intelligence (standardize scores)											
Mean age of assessment	0.21	0.18	(-0.15, 0.57)	0.262	0.0	1.25	1	0.262	8.26	3	0.041
NDVI pregnancy vs. Internalization problems (z-score)											
Mean age of assessment	0.01	0.01	(-0.01, 0.03)	0.357	0.0	0.849	1	0.356	22.62	5	<0.001
NDVI childhood vs. Internalization problems (z-score)											
Mean age of assessment	-0.04	0.01	(-0.05, -0.02)	<0.001	98.0	15.67	1	<0.001	2.46	4	0.651
NDVI childhood vs. Externalization problems (z-score)											

Mean age of assessment	-0.02	0.01	(-0.04, 0.00)	0.117	51.7	2.452	1	0.117	6.26	4	0.180
Linear distance childhood vs. ADHD symptoms (z-score)											
Mean age of assessment	0.00	0.01	(-0.01, 0.01)	0.746	0.0	0.104	1	0.746	11.23	5	0.047

se = standard error of beta-coefficient (estimate)

Table S17 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis to green spaces exposures and z-scores or age-standardized outcomes without considering adjustments for child age and sex. Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Outcome	Main models β (95%CI)	Sample	Without adjustment for sex and/or age	p-value	Sample	I₂ (%)	p Q test
Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore)							
NDVI_pregnancy	0.02 (-0.02; 0.06)	7994	0.02 (-0.02;0.06)	0.257	7994	28.4	0.250
NDVI_childhood	0.06 (0.03; 0.09)	7908	0.06 (0.03;0.09)	<0.001	7908	1.77	0.632
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06;0.03)	7679	-0.01 (-0.05; 0.02)	0.446	7679	51.3	0.107
Linear Distance (m) childhood	-0.04 (-0.08; -0.01)	7488	-0.04 (-0.07; -0.01)	0.005	7488	22.9	0.277
Lung function (FVC zscore)							
NDVI_pregnancy	0.01 (-0.02;0.04)	7958	0.01 (-0.02;0.04)	0.419	7958	0.0	0.410
NDVI_childhood	0.07 (0.04; 0.09)	7872	0.06 (0.04;0.09)	<0.001	7872	0.0	0.715
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06; 0.03)	7643	-0.01 (-0.05;0.03)	0.549	7643	43.9	0.159
Linear Distance (m) childhood	-0.04 (-0.07; -0.02)	7452	-0.04 (-0.07; -0.02)	0.001	7452	0.0	0.558
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC zscore)							
NDVI_pregnancy	0.00 (-0.03; 0.03)	7958	0.00 (-0.03;0.03)	0.928	7958	0.37	0.312
NDVI_childhood	-0.02 (-0.05; 0.01)	7872	-0.02 (-0.04;0.01)	0.273	7872	0.10	0.351
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	0.00 (-0.03; 0.03)	7643	-0.00 (-0.03;0.03)	0.942	7643	27.91	0.155
Linear Distance (m) childhood	0.01 (-0.03; 0.05)	7452	0.02 (-0.03;0.05)	0.616	7452	58.3	0.074
BMI (z-score)							

NDVI_pregnancy	0.01 (-0.01;0.03)	35407	0.01 (-0.01; 0.03)	0.319	35407	0.0	0.626
NDVI_childhood	0.00 (-0.2; 0.02)	27491	-0.00 (-0.02;0.02)	0.802	27491	0.0	0.813
Linear Distance (m) _pregnancy	-0.01 (-0.03; 0.0)	35848	-0.01 (-0.03; 0.02)	0.084	34848	1.31	0.348
Linear Distance (m) _childhood	0.00 (-0.02; 0.01)	26597	-0.00 (-0.02;0.01)	0.752	26597	0.04	0.625
Non-verbal intelligence standardize score per age							
NDVI_pregnancy	-0.46 (-1.16;0.25)	12505	-0.50 (-1.21; 0.19)	0.159	12837	65.6	0.007
NDVI_childhood	0.02 (-0.68; 0.65)	12352	-0.04 (-0.68; 0.61)	0.913	12610	66.16	0.041
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	0.22 (-0.10; 0.53)	12058	0.21 (-0.10; 0.52)	0.184	12315	0	0.505
Linear Distance (m) childhood	0.07 (-0.24; 0.38)	11642	0.08 (-0.21; 0.38)	0.579	11832	0	0.909

Overall adjusted estimates with 95% CIs from IPD meta-analyses of the outcome-specific regression models, where cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects model (inversed-variance). Main models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI. Specific-cohort adjustment included maternal ethnic background and sub-cohort. Neurodevelopmental outcomes were further adjusted by cohort-specific instrument and /or evaluator. β = Beta estimates and corresponding 95% confidence intervals. Sample (pooled cohorts' sample). P-value = statistical significance of pooled effect size, I^2 -statistics (I^2), p_{Qtest} = pvalue for heterogeneity Q Cochran's test.

Table S18- Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and lung function further adjusted by nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Outcome	Main models β (95%CI)	Sample	Further adjusted for NO₂ β (95%CI)	p-value	Sample	I₂ (%)	p Q test
Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore)							
NDVI pregnancy	0.02 (-0.02; 0.06)	7994	0.01 (-0.02; 0.06)	0.434	5606	0,0	0.726
NDVI childhood	0.06 (0.03; 0.09)	7908	0.06 (0.02; 0.10)	0.005	5551	0.0	0.749
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06; 0.03)	7679	-0.01 (-0.05; 0.02)	0.497	5292	34.0	0.211
Linear Distance (m) childhood	-0.04 (-0.08; -0.01)	7488	-0.05 (-0.08; -0.01)	0.001	5170	0.0	0.579
Lung function (FVC_{-zscore})							
NDVI pregnancy	0.01 (-0.02; 0.04)	7958	-0.00 (-0.04; 0.04)	0.918	5571	0.0	0.603
NDVI childhood	0.07 (0.04; 0.09)	7872	0.05 (0.01; 0.10)	0.012	5516	0.0	0.835
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06; 0.03)	7643	-0.01 (-0.06; 0.04)	0.667	5257	50.0	0.108
Linear Distance (m) childhood	-0.04 (-0.07; -0.02)	7452	-0.05 (-0.08; -0.02)	0.001	5135	0.0	0.867
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC_{-zscore})							
NDVI pregnancy	0.00 (-0.03; 0.03)	7958	0.02 (0.02; 0.06)	0.308	5571	0.0	0.548
NDVI childhood	0.00 (0.03; 0.03)	7872	0.02 (-0.03; 0,05)	0.706	5516	0.0	0.816
Linear Distance (m) pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.05; 0.01)	7643	0.01 (-0.04; 0.03)	0.855	5257	18.2	0.231
Linear Distance (m) childhood	0.01 (-0.03; 0.05)	7452	0.00 (-0.03; 0,04)	0.860	5135	16.8	0.304

Overall adjusted estimates with 95% CIs from IPD meta-analyses of the outcome-specific regression models, where cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects model (inversed-variance). Main models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI. Specific-cohort adjustment included maternal ethnic background and sub-cohort (city). Neurodevelopmental outcomes were further adjusted by cohort-specific instrument and /or evaluator. **β** = Beta estimates and corresponding 95% confidence intervals. Sample (pooled cohorts' sample). P-value = statistical significance of pooled effect size, I²-statistics (I₂), p_Qtest = pvalue for heterogeneity Q Cochran's test.

Table S19 - Pooled effect estimates from two-stage meta-analysis for exposure to green spaces and lung function further adjusted by Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}). Regression estimates are represented per one IQR increase in each exposure.

Outcome	Main models β (95%CI)	Sample	Further adjusted for PM_{2.5} β (95%CI)	p-value	Sample	I² (%)	p Q test
Lung Function (FEV₁ zscore)							
NDVI pregnancy	0.02 (-0.02; 0.06)	7994	0.02 (-0.02; 0.06)	0.285	5173	0.0	0.760
NDVI_childhood	0.06 (0.03; 0.09)	7908	0.06 (0.02; 0.10)	0.002	5135	0.0	0.667
Distance_pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06; 0.03)	7679	-0.01 (-0.05; 0.02)	0.435	4860	25.3	0.249
Distance_childhood	-0.04 (-0.08; -0.01)	7488	-0.05 (-0.08; -0.02)	0.001	4755	0.0	0.622
Lung function (FVC - zscore)							
NDVI pregnancy	0.01 (-0.02; 0.04)	7958	0.01 (-0.03; 0.05)	0.700	5144	0.0	0.694
NDVI_childhood	0.07 (0.04; 0.09)	7872	0.05 (0.02; 0.10)	0.013	5106	0.0	0.530
Distance_pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.06; 0.03)	7643	-0.01 (-0.06; 0.03)	0.546	4831	41.0	0.168
Distance_childhood	-0.04 (-0.07; -0.02)	7452	-0.05 (-0.08; -0.02)	0.001	4726	0.0	0.962
Lung function (FEV₁/FVC-zscore)							
NDVI pregnancy	0.00 (-0.03; 0.03)	7958	0.01 (-0.03; 0.05)	0.657	5144	0.0	0.585
NDVI_childhood	0.00 (0.03; 0.03)	7872	-0.00 (-0.05; 0.04)	0.796	5106	0.0	0.536
Distance_pregnancy	-0.02 (-0.05; 0.01)	7643	-0.01 (-0.04; 0.04)	0.977	4831	33.4	0.177
Distance_childhood	0.01 (-0.03; 0.05)	7452	0.01 (-0.04; 0.06)	0.775	4726	52.8	0.095

Overall adjusted estimates with 95% CIs from IPD meta-analyses of the outcome-specific regression models, where cohorts were assigned weights under the random-effects model (inversed-variance). Models are adjusted for: child age and sex, maternal education, area-level SES smoking during pregnancy, parity, maternal age, and maternal BMI. Specific-cohort adjustment included mother country of birth and sub-cohort. Neurodevelopmental outcomes were further adjusted by cohort-specific instrument and /or evaluator. **β** = Beta estimates and corresponding 95% confidence intervals. Sample (pooled cohorts' sample). P-value = statistical significance of pooled effect size, I²-statistics (I²), p_Qtest = pvalue for heterogeneity Q Cochran's test.